

M5.1: Detailed planning of collaborations with research infrastructures in Europe and internationally

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Introduction

Over the next 12 months, this task will focus on fostering new collaborations and strengthening existing partnerships with Research Infrastructures (RIs) across Europe and other regions worldwide.

Within Europe, the emphasis will be on strategic dialogues with RIs on the ESFRI roadmap and the development of collaboration strategies in key priority areas. These efforts will benefit from consultation with ELIXIR Node partners and aim to align activities between European RIs, enhancing bioinformatics and life science research and RIs. Recognising the shared membership of ELIXIR with multiple RIs, this task will allow the alignment of strategic, scientific and technical priorities.

Beyond Europe, the task will raise awareness of ELIXIR's services and resources and enable knowledge exchange with bioinformatics communities worldwide. By building on past and ongoing projects in Latin America, Africa, and beyond, the task will explore the value of distributed RIs and embed best practices into future Node activities. Through these efforts, the task aims to enhance global scientific collaboration and embed ELIXIR's role in the international research landscape.

This planning will serve as a guiding document for the duration of STEERS project. It begins by addressing collaboration with RIs in Europe, outlines expected collaborations with global organisations and geographical regions, and concludes with an overview of communication channels and potential support mechanisms for Nodes in their international engagement.

Research Infrastructure Collaborations in Europe

To enhance our understanding of interactions between ELIXIR Nodes and other ESFRI Research Infrastructures (RIs), the ELIXIR Hub has launched a pilot exercise to assess optimal methods for capturing these interactions in a way that benefits both the Hub and the Nodes. In 2024, the Hub began testing a tool with selected Nodes to gather this information

effectively, and based on the feedback collected, the Hub plans to refine and implement the tool in 2025 before rolling out a broader mapping initiative.

Outlined below are key collaborations, both current and anticipated, as part of ELIXIR-STEERS T5.4 activities:

- **Instruct-ERIC:** In December 2024, ELIXIR formalised a collaboration with INSTRUCT-ERIC by signing a [Memorandum of Understanding](#). This agreement acknowledges our shared goals and overlapping areas of interest, setting the stage for increased synergy between the two RIs.
- **Euro-BioImaging:** In January 2025, the Hub plans to sign a Memorandum of Understanding as a renewal of the strategic collaboration first established with the Imaging Data Strategy, initially signed with [Euro-BioImaging in 2014](#). This will align recent advancements within both organisations, particularly supporting the common vision to enable excellent interdisciplinary research across Europe and globally, based on the wealth of knowledge also derived from combining imaging data and biomolecular data.
- **DiSSCo:** In 2025, we aim to establish a formal Collaboration Strategy with the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo). This partnership will bridge ELIXIR's Biodiversity Community with DiSSCo, fostering data sharing and collaborative opportunities in biodiversity research, in line with the priorities set out in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-28.
- **BBMRI-ERIC:** We will continue to collaborate with BBMRI under the auspices of the ELIXIR - BBMRI Statement of Intent signed in 2023.

Global Research Infrastructure Collaborations

On a global scale, ELIXIR has solidified partnerships with international RIs to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaborative research:

- **National Institutes of Health (NIH):** In September 2024, the ELIXIR Hub formalised a [Memorandum of Agreement \(MoA\)](#) with the National Institutes of Health's Office for Data Science Strategy (ODSS), recognising our longstanding, informal collaborations. This agreement builds on years of cooperation, including staff exchanges, joint events, workshops and regular inter-organisational meetings.
- **Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF):** Looking ahead, ELIXIR will seek to develop a collaboration strategy with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) to further support global biodiversity data initiatives and support biodiversity activities in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-28.
- **Genome Canada:** The Hub will explore possibilities to deepen collaborations with Genome Canada in 2025, aligning activities around sensitive human data including the EU projects coordinated by ELIXIR in this domain (such as Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI)).

Planned Collaborations with Latin America and Africa

As part of the ongoing update to ELIXIR's International Strategy, the ELIXIR Hub aims to include targeted steps to enhance engagement with the bioinformatics communities in Latin America, Africa and Canada. These steps are designed to raise awareness about ELIXIR's resources beyond Europe and foster collaboration opportunities between the Nodes and these regions. Below are some early initiatives launched under the ELIXIR-STEERS T5.4 framework:

Latin America:

- **Argentina:** ELIXIR Italy is organising a Roadshow in Argentina, scheduled for mid-April 2025, with support from the Italian Embassy in Argentina. This event will engage local bioinformatics communities, aiming to foster dialogue and partnerships. Additional ELIXIR Nodes, such as ELIXIR Hungary, ELIXIR Belgium and the EMBL-EBI, are expected to join the Roadshow, reinforcing ELIXIR's commitment to building connections across Latin America.
- **Brazil:** Following up on the previous staff exchange with Brazilian partners in 2023, future plans include organising other training events in Brazil in 2025 covering topics such as the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer, FAIR training and Research Data Management.
- **Chile:** The ELIXIR infrastructure and its main services were presented during a dedicated session at the 4th Annual Latin America Visit of the HORIZON 2020 MSCA RISE project REFRACT (GA 823886). The event was held on 18 April 2024 at the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile in Santiago, Chile. The session aimed to showcase ELIXIR's services and activities, including ELIXIR-STEERS, to the local life sciences research community.
- **Colombia:** ELIXIR was represented at the ISCB-Latin America SolBio CCBCOL Conference on Bioinformatics 2024, organised by the Colombian Conference for Bioinformatics (CCBCOL) in collaboration with the Iberoamerican Society of Bioinformatics (SolBio) and the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB). The event, which was attended by representatives from ELIXIR Spain, the EMBL-EBI and the ELIXIR Hub, aimed to promote scientific and professional exchange in bioinformatics across Latin America, attracted over 200 participants. ELIXIR actively contributed to discussions during a roundtable session, supporting regional engagement and knowledge exchange.

Africa:

- **African Bioinformatics Institute (ABI):** In anticipation of the upcoming African Bioinformatics Institute, the ELIXIR Hub has attended ABI information webinars to explore collaboration opportunities with the African bioinformatics community. In

November 2024, a meeting was held with Prof Nicola Mulder to learn more about the ABI project and discuss potential areas for future collaboration between ELIXIR and ABI.

One potential topic where ELIXIR could serve as a bridge between regions is by comparing successful models for bioinformatics infrastructures. By sharing evidence-based frameworks, legal models and experience, ELIXIR can foster dialogue and knowledge exchange between Europe, Africa, Latin America and North America and our Nodes. Colleagues at EMBL-EBI are actively exploring collaborative ways to build science infrastructures that are truly global and equitable through their global engagement work.

Communications and International Engagement Support

Throughout the duration of the project, the ELIXIR Hub will continue to support staff exchanges with international partners, aiming to equip ELIXIR Nodes with enhanced tools for global engagement. These tools could include factsheets and interactive workshops designed to support Nodes in navigating and expanding their international partnerships.

1. Material to support the Nodes in their applications to the [ELIXIR Staff Exchange](#) in countries beyond Europe as well as other international mobility/exchange schemes such as Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA) Staff Exchange.
2. Raise awareness on how to engage and build equitable partnerships with other regions beyond Europe through workshops and seminars.

To further showcase ELIXIR's European and international collaborations, the ELIXIR Hub has refreshed its communication channels, highlighting key engagements and achievements through ELIXIR's [webpage](#). Additionally, an international Slack channel has been launched within the ELIXIR-wide workspace to foster discussion on international topics and share engagement opportunities across the Nodes. The use of this resource will continue to be developed and encouraged to share information that benefits the wider ELIXIR community.

In conclusion, this planning document serves as a roadmap for activities in 2025. It outlines the collaborations with partners within and beyond Europe, which will be based on priorities set out in the ELIXIR International Strategy, scheduled to be launched in 2025.

Defining priorities in the ELIXIR International Strategy

To allow ELIXIR internal and external stakeholders to understand ELIXIR's priorities with regards to international engagement activities in the future, efforts in Task 5.4 have included the revision of the ELIXIR International Strategy. After a consultation with ELIXIR Node partners with active global engagement in Task 5.4, the revised Strategy will detail the main regions and areas for collaboration in the scientific and technological field, as well as detail

mechanisms for international engagement. The publication of the revised Strategy is foreseen in the second quarter of 2025.

In Conclusion

This planning document serves as a roadmap for T5.4 activities for the duration of STEERS, focusing on fostering collaborations within and beyond Europe. These efforts are aligned with priorities set out in the forthcoming ELIXIR International Strategy, which is scheduled for launch in early 2025.

